

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC

D6: Report on transient methods optimised for determining thermal conductivity of thin films or coatings of PRC materials with a target uncertainty below 10 %

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Glossary

ASTM	American society for testing and materials
DSC	differential scanning calorimetry
GUM	guide to the uncertainty of measurement
IR	infrared
LFA	light/laser flash analysis
LVDT	linear Variable Differential Transformer
MCT	mercury cadmium telluride
PRC	passive radiative cooling
PRCF	passive radiative cooling foil
TPS	transient plane source
MDSC	modulated differential scanning calorimetry
TIM	thermal interface material

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1. Summary

In the framework of the PaRaMetriC project, a work package is dedicated to the determination of the thermal conductivity of thin films or coatings of PRC materials using transient methods. The resulting target uncertainty that should be obtained should be below 10%.

For the determination of the thermal conductivity λ of these materials, the thermal diffusivity a and the specific heat capacity c_p were determined separately using light/laser flash analysis (LFA) and modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC). By multiplying the thermal diffusivity a , the specific heat capacity c_p and the density ρ , the thermal conductivity λ can be derived.

Furthermore, measurements using the transient plane source (TPS) method were performed for a direct measurement of the thermal conductivity as an additional method with higher uncertainty for comparison.

In this work package, several materials were examined, namely Spacecool, 3M Gen4 PRCF and V98RF (Cooling Photonics coating on Almecco Vega 98®) as well as three modified foils from the manufacturer Spacecool.

Within PaRaMetriC, measurements were performed at CAE and PTB, as well as at Netzsch and Linseis on behalf of FIW using complementary transient techniques:

- light/laser flash analysis (LFA) to obtain thermal diffusivity a :
at CAE and Netzsch a Netzsch LFA 467 HyperFlash with an LN₂-cooled MCT detector has been used. The thermal conductivity λ is then derived the thermal diffusivity a , the specific heat capacity c_p and the density ρ by multiplying these values: $\lambda = a \cdot c_p \cdot \rho$.
- modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC) to determine specific heat capacity c_p :
at CAE a TA Instruments Q2000 has been used.
- transient plane source (TPS) as an additional method for directly measuring the thermal conductivity:
at PTB a Hot Disk 2500 has been used with variants for double-sided, single-sided and thin-film evaluations on layered stacks.
- thermal Interface Material (TIM) Tester from Linseis as a further method for directly measuring the thermal conductivity.

The derived relative expanded uncertainty for an expansion factor of $k = 2$ is $U_\lambda / \lambda = 8.7 \%$ for using LFA and MDSC measurements and therefore lies below 10 % meeting the D6 target. Although the TPS method yields reliable thermal conductivities for bulk sheets and well-controlled geometries, the relative expanded uncertainty for very thin coatings on metal is significantly higher and ranges around 20 % to 30 %.

2. Introduction

Passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials offer a pathway to reduce building cooling loads and urban heat through tailored radiative properties in the solar and thermal-infrared ranges. To predict and compare the performance of such materials in real applications, reliable thermal data are required in addition to their optical and infrared-optical spectral characteristics. In particular, the thermal conductivity of thin films and coatings used in PRC stacks is a key input for heat-balance models that couple conduction within the stack to radiative exchange with the atmosphere and space. The PaRaMetriC project therefore included a dedicated activity (Task 3.3) to establish accurate, traceable and practically applicable transient methods for determining the thermal conductivity of thin PRC layers with target relative uncertainty below 10 %. This activity culminates in the present deliverable D6 (Report on transient methods optimised for determining thermal conductivity of thin films or coatings of PRC materials with a target uncertainty below 10 %).

Measuring the thermal conductivity of PRC films and coatings poses specific metrological challenges. PRC layers are often (i) very thin (below 1 mm), (ii) laminated on highly conductive, reflective substrates (e.g. aluminium, copper or silver-based mirrors), (iii) multilayered (optical stacks, tie-layers, adhesives), and (iv) subject to interfacial effects such as thermal contact resistance and native oxide layers (e.g. Al_2O_3) that bias transient measurements if unaccounted.

Within PaRaMetriC, measurements were performed at CAE, FIW and PTB, using complementary transient techniques:

- light/laser flash analysis (LFA) to obtain thermal diffusivity a :
at CAE and Netzsch a Netzsch LFA 467 HyperFlash with an LN_2 -cooled MCT detector has been used. The thermal conductivity λ is then derived the thermal diffusivity a , the specific heat capacity c_p and the density ρ by multiplying these values: $\lambda = a \cdot c_p \cdot \rho$.
- modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC) to determine specific heat capacity c_p :
at CAE a TA Instruments Q2000 has been used.
- transient plane source (TPS) as an additional method for directly measuring the thermal conductivity:
at PTB a Hot Disk 2500 has been used with variants for double-sided, single-sided and thin-film evaluations on layered stacks.
- thermal Interface Material (TIM) Tester from Linseis as a further method for directly measuring the thermal conductivity.

The transient plane source (TPS) has been chosen as a further method with higher uncertainty for comparison.

This deliverable reports the procedures, applicability limits, uncertainty budgets, and comparative results for these methods on representative PRC-materials, including the following products: SPACECOOL, 3M Gen4 PRCF and V98RF (Cooling Photonics coating on Almeco Vega 98®). Specimens encompass free-standing films and film-on-metal configurations prepared expressly for LFA and MDSC as well as TPS.

3. Procedures for determining the thermophysical properties

3.1 Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (MDSC)

Temperature modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC) is a standard method for the determination of the specific heat capacity c_p [1-3]. In Figure 1, a schematic drawing of a DSC or MDSC furnace is shown.

Figure 1: Sketch of the experimental setup for DSC and MDSC measurements.

In this method, two small crucibles are exposed to a temperature regime. One of the crucibles contains a specimen made of the material of interest. The temperature of both crucibles is recorded as a function of time. The heat flow in the specimen is calculated from the temperature difference between the empty crucible and the crucible containing the specimen by an additional calibration measurement using a specimen with known heat capacity, i.e. a disc made of sapphire. With modulated DSC the temperature program contains a linear increase, which might also be zero for quasi-isothermal measurements, and a sinusoidally oscillating contribution. Both the material property (specific heat capacity c_p) and information about irreversible thermal effects are obtained by a special evaluation.

Ideally, the specimens for MDSC measurements should be small disks with a diameter of approximately 5 mm, a thickness lower than 1.5 mm and a mass between 10 and 30 mg.

All DSC and MDSC measurements executed at CAE were performed using a Q2000 apparatus from TA Instruments.

3.2 Light/laser Flash Analysis (LFA)

The thermal diffusivity a has been measured at CAE and Netzsch using the light/laser flash method [4-7]. The front of a disc-shaped specimen under investigation is heated with a short heat pulse, for example generated using a laser or a flash lamp (Figure 2). The heat introduced in this way spreads over the whole specimen, also heating the back. The time needed for this process is determined by the thermal diffusivity a . An infrared detector records the temperature rise of the backside of the specimen as a function of time. The time-temperature curve is mathematically analysed using analytical models to determine the thermal diffusivity a . The resulting curve is fitted with a theoretical model using the specimen thickness at ambient temperature. Heat losses and the finite length of the heat pulse as well as the possible influence of direct heat transfer by radiation between the front and the back side of the specimen are also taken into account by the evaluation procedure. Prior to the measurement, a thin layer of graphite is applied on both sides of each specimen for a better absorption of the pulse energy on the front side and for a higher emissivity of the rear side.

Figure 2: Sketch of the experimental setup of the LFA.

For appropriate specimens it is also possible to perform measurements on multilayer systems and thus determine the thermal diffusivity of one of the layers. The thermophysical properties of the other layer as well as the density ρ and the specific heat capacity c_p of the layer with the unknown thermal diffusivity must be known for the data evaluation.

All measurements at CAE and Netzsch were performed using a LFA 467 Hyperflash apparatus from Netzsch Gerätebau GmbH. In this apparatus, a xenon flash lamp is used as source for the heat pulse and a liquid nitrogen cooled mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) detector is used for the detection of the infrared (IR) radiation at the rear side of the specimen.

According to the manufacturer, the hyperflash system meets the requirements of ASTM E1461 and ASTM E2585.

An ideal specimen for flash measurements would be disk-shaped with a diameter of 12.7 mm and a thickness smaller than 3 mm. The surfaces of the specimen should be plane-parallel and even. For multilayer specimens, the thickness of the specimen with the unknown thermophysical properties and the specimen with the known thermophysical properties must be adjusted according to the properties of the specimens.

3.2.1 Determination of the density and calculation of the thermal conductivity

Additionally the density ρ of the investigated specimens has been measured and finally the thermal conductivity λ is calculated by multiplying the thermal diffusivity a , the specific heat capacity c_p and the density ρ of the specimen:

$$\lambda(T) = a(T) \cdot \rho(T) \cdot c_p(T) \quad (1)$$

The values have been determined in dependence on temperature — except the density, which is only measured as ambient temperature. Due to the relatively low temperature range, the temperature dependence of the density of the specimens can be neglected.

3.3 Transient Plane Source (TPS)

3.3.1 Thermal conductivity measurement

The thermal conductivity of the samples was measured using the Hot Disk 2500 thermal constants analyser, which is capable of analysing isotropic bulk materials with thermal conductivities ranging from 0.3 W/(m·K) to 500 W/(m·K) (Hot Disk Manual, 2022). For each sample, measurement parameters, including heating power, measurement time, and sensor configuration, were carefully optimized to ensure high accuracy.

Given the layered structure of the PRC samples, additional attention was paid to data interpretation, including appropriate selection of start and end points during analysis. The thermal conductivity values obtained for the aluminium alloy substrates aligned well with reference data for Al 6600, while the influence of the aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) layers was also accounted for.

Since the measured PRC samples were thin and, in many cases, only a single piece was available, the measurement methods described in Sections 3.3.2 - 3.3.5 were applied accordingly.

3.3.2 Sample Placement and Sensor Centering

The Hot Disk system supplies constant power to an initially isothermal sample via a Hot Disk sensor, which also functions as a resistance thermometer during a limited heating period. The temperature increase, reflected in the sensor's resistance changes, is precisely recorded and analysed to determine both thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity from a single transient recording. Hot Disk sensors are placed between the plane surfaces of two sample pieces of the material under investigation.

3.3.3 Single-sided testing

Single-sided testing follows the same procedure as double-sided testing, except one sample half is replaced by an insulating material (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Sample setup for single-sided testing.

The insulating material should have a thermal conductivity at least 10 times lower than the sample and a thermal diffusivity not exceeding that of the sample.

3.3.4 Thin-Film Thermal Resistance Measurements

Thin-film measurements were conducted using a dedicated Thermal Resistance (Thin Film) module. In this method, thin films (applied to aluminium slabs using an adhesive) were evaluated using two steps:

- Step 1: Measure the thermal conductivity of the bare aluminium substrate.
- Step 2: Enter the known substrate conductivity, film thickness, and sensor type into the software to evaluate the film.

Both steps must be performed under identical conditions, including pressure (using a reference brass weight), measurement duration, and heating temperature.

During data analysis, the residual plot must be examined. A deviation from random scatter at the beginning of the curve typically indicates a delay in establishing steady heat flow: especially with thicker films. In such cases, the initial data points should be excluded. This exclusion is more common in sample measurements than in reference tests.

3.3.5 Oxide Layers in Metal Samples

When analyzing metal samples with surface oxide layers, it is essential to treat them as layered structures. The overall (or equivalent) thermal conductivity is not simply that of the base metal but a function of the thermal properties and thicknesses of each individual layer. To determine the effective thermal conductivity λ_{equiv} of such a multilayer system, the following relation is used:

$$\sum \frac{\delta_i}{\lambda_i} = \frac{\delta_{equiv}}{\lambda_{equiv}} \quad (2)$$

- δ_{equiv} - effective thickness of the multilayer structure,
- λ_{equiv} - equiv. thermal conductivity of multilayer structure,
- δ_i - thickness of a layer in a multilayer structure,
- λ_i - thermal conductivity of a layer in a multilayer structure.

The thickness of the Al_2O_3 (aluminium oxide) layer formed on aluminium surfaces can vary significantly: typically ranging from 0.1 nm to 100 μm , depending on storage, oxidation conditions, and surface processing. For example, consider a 5 mm thick aluminium plate with a measured effective thermal conductivity of 178 $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$. If the plate has a 60 μm thick Al_2O_3 layer with a known thermal conductivity of 40 $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$, the corrected thermal conductivity of the pure aluminium core is calculated to be approximately 220 $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$ — a value that aligns with standard reference data for aluminium alloys.

3.4 Thermal Interface Material Tester

3.4.1 Measurement setup and measurement principle

3.4.1.1 Stationary measurement method (ASTM D5470)

Measuring the thermal conductivity of thin layers using stationary methods is very difficult, as the thermal resistance is very low even in insulating materials, resulting in a very small temperature difference at the test specimen, which causes high measurement uncertainties.

Even transient methods (e.g., laser flash method) require a minimum test specimen thickness or fail due to the layer structure of the PDRC materials under investigation. In addition, when the thermal resistance of the layers is very low, the heat transfer resistances at the surfaces and the contact resistances between the individual layers also become important.

For this reason, the thermal interface material (TIM) test method described below is used, which was developed for the investigation of thermal pastes, contact layers, and uneven surfaces.

A rectangular test specimen of the material to be tested (25 mm x 25 mm) is clamped between a heated and a cooled meter bar. The hot meter bar is heated to a controlled temperature, while the cold meter bar is constantly cooled by a liquid-cooled block, ensuring that a constant heat flow passes through the test specimen. An adjustable clamping pressure (1 MPa and 1.5 MPa) ensures reproducible surface contacts, while the test specimen thickness is measured using an integrated linear variable differential transformer (LVDT). In Figure 4, the experimental setup is shown.

Figure 4: Sketch and experimental setup for thermal conductivity measurements with TIM-tester.

3.4.1.2 Heat flow and temperature measurement

Several temperature sensors are installed at defined intervals in the metering bars, which measure the temperature gradient across the meter bar and the test specimen in a steady state. The total thermal resistance

of the layer can be calculated because the thermal conductivity of the meter bar and the space between the temperature sensors is known. From the measured temperature difference ΔT between the hot and cold measuring points and the known heat flow \dot{Q} , R_{th} is calculated.

$$\dot{Q} = \frac{\lambda_{meter\ bar} \cdot A}{l} \cdot (T_1 - T_2)$$

$$R_{th} = \frac{\Delta T}{\dot{Q}}$$

3.4.2 Evolution and calculation of thermal properties

3.4.2.1 Total thermal resistance

The determined R_{th} (thermal impedance) includes both the thermal resistance of the material and contact resistances at the interfaces. In the case of soft or uneven TIM test specimens, the contact resistance (heat transfer resistance) is particularly relevant, as it contributes to the total impedance. By varying the layer thickness d (measurement of several stacked test specimens), the proportional material resistance can be isolated. To determine the thermal conductivity, R_{th} of the different thicknesses is plotted against d . The linear analysis shows the contact resistance as the y -axis intercept and the thermal conductivity λ as the reciprocal of the slope. Overall, the TIM tester works according to the steady-state heat flow measurement method and combines pressure and thickness control with measured temperature difference to determine R_{th} and λ_{eff} .

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{d}{R_{th} \cdot A}$$

3.4.2.2 Measurement uncertainty

The manufacturer LINSEIS specifies a measurement accuracy of approximately ± 3 – 5 % for the thermal impedance of the TIM tester L58, with a repeatability (reproducibility) of ± 2 %. The measuring range for effective thermal conductivity λ_{eff} is approximately $0.1 \dots 50$ W/(m·K) (corresponding to thermal impedances of approximately 0.005 – 500 cm²·K/W) and the contact pressure can be adjusted up to approximately $0 \dots 8$ MPa (for the 25 mm x 25 mm cross section). The test specimen thickness (0.01 to 8 mm) is measured using a high-resolution LVDT probe (within a range of ± 1 μ m). Several integrated temperature sensors in the measuring bodies detect the temperature difference through the test specimen. No explicit information on the resolution of these sensors (or the pressure control) can be found in the publicly available specifications.

4. Specimens

4.1 SPACECOOL

The specimen “Spacecool” was provided by the manufacturer SPACECOOL Inc. and consists of a self-adhesive multilayer silver-polymer optical film with specular reflection and surface roughness-induced light scattering.

For the flash measurements, circular specimens were provided with a diameter of 25 mm. These specimens consisted of an aluminium disk with the adhesive film on top. The thickness of the aluminium disk was 0.506 mm, the thickness of the film was 0.118 mm, and the density of the film was $\rho = (1216 \pm 61) \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$. In Figure 5, the specimen “Spacecool” is shown as it was provided for the measurements. A separate sample of the aluminium disk was also provided for the determination of the thermophysical properties of this material, as these properties are needed for the data evaluation of the multilayer measurements.

Figure 5: The picture shows the specimen “Spacecool”, which is a thin, self-adhesive film applied on an aluminium substrate. The specimen shown in this picture was used for the LFA and MDSC measurements.

For the hot-disk measurements, the self-adhesive film was applied to an aluminium substrate with a diameter of 50 mm and a thickness of 5 mm. The thickness of the PRCF-film was 0.1 mm. In Figure 6, the specimen provided by the manufacturer for the hot disk measurements is shown.

Figure 6: Photo of the hot disk specimen of the optical foil from the company SPACECOOL.

4.2 "V98RF" of Cooling Photonics S.L. and Almeco Group

A selective emitting polymer "RF" developed by Cooling Photonics was applied on a silver-based mirror labeled "Vega 98®" (V98) cut to size 40 mm x 40 mm provided by Almeco Group. "Vega 98®" is a specially designed highly reflective surface. It consists in a high-purity aluminium substrate, enhanced by a specific PVD multilayer coating system based on silver. Vega 98 is manufactured on a continuous coil vacuum coating plant, which makes it a fully scalable product. The RF coating preserves the high reflectivity of the V98 substrate while providing high emissivity in the IR atmospheric window, resulting in a high-performance selective emitter (V98RF).

One specimen, which is shown in Figure 7, was provided for Hot Disk measurements. The thickness of the PRC film was 18 μm .

Figure 7: Photo of the selected PRC material: joint development of Cooling Photonics and Almeco "V98RF".

4.3 3M R&D PRCF

The material “3M R&D PRCF” is a self-adhesive metal-free white-diffuse R&D developmental passive radiative cooling foil (PRCF) provided by 3M, which is also titled as “3M Gen4 PRCF” by the manufacturer.

For the LFA measurements, the material was applied on an aluminium substrate with a diameter of 25 mm. The thickness of the aluminium disk was 0.508 mm, the thickness of the foil was 0.197 mm and the density of the foil was $\rho = (840 \pm 42) \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$. In Figure 8, a photo of the LFA specimen is shown. Additionally to the measurement as a two-layer system it was also possible to perform a flash measurement on a free-standing layer of the 3M PRCF specimen as it was possible to remove the PRCF layer from the aluminium disk. The thickness of the free-standing specimen was 0.206 mm.

Figure 8: The specimen „3M R&D PRCF“, which is a thin film applied on an aluminium substrate. The picture shows the specimens used for LFA and MDSC measurements.

For the hot disk measurements, the PRCF foil was adhered on an aluminium substrate of 90 mm in diameter using a thermal paste Apiezon. The specimen used for the hot disk measurements is shown in Figure 9. The thickness of the PRCF film was 200 μm , the thickness of the entire system was 5 mm.

Figure 9: Photo of the Hot Disk specimen of the material R&D developmental PRCF from 3M "3M R&D PRCF".

4.4 SPACECOOL, additional samples

In addition to the first SPACECOOL sample, which was introduced in chapter 4.1, the manufacturer SPACECOOL prepared three further samples, which exhibit additional properties with respect to practical application. These samples were designated as sample 1, sample 2 and sample 3. Sample 1 was a water proof design, sample 2 was equipped with an adhesive backside and sample 3 was equipped with a magnetic backside. Larger sheets of these samples were provided for the LFA and MDSC measurements and specimens with adequate sizes were prepared. For the LFA measurements, disks with a diameter of 12.7 mm were prepared. For sample 1, the thickness of the specimen for the flash measurements was 1.635 mm, the density was $\rho = (1360 \pm 68) \frac{kg}{m^3}$. For sample 2, the thickness of the specimen for the flash measurements was 0.204 mm (without the foil to protect the adhesive backside), the density was $\rho = (1337 \pm 67) \frac{kg}{m^3}$. For sample 3, the thickness of the specimen for the flash measurements was 0.608 mm and the density was $\rho = (2508 \pm 125) \frac{kg}{m^3}$. In Figure 10, the samples from which the specimens for the LFA and the MDSC measurements were prepared are shown.

Figure 10: Three additional samples manufactured by SPACECOOL. Sample 1 (top) was a water proof design, sample 2 (middle) was a design with an adhesive backside and sample 3 (bottom) was a design with a magnetic backside. From these samples, the specimens for the LFA and MDSC measurements were prepared.

Of the first sample with the waterproof design also a specimen for Hot Disk measurements was provided. This specimen consisted of two halves: the front part is white, and the back part is black. The specimen had a thickness of 1.63 mm and is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Sample 1 from the company SPACECOOL with a waterproof design. The picture shows the specimen for the Hot Disk measurements.

5. Results

5.1 TIM-Tester measurements

5.1.1 Measurements on the SpaceCool test specimen

To measure the Spacecool test specimens, three 25 mm x 25 mm test specimens were cut from a large sheet of the specimen that was provided by the manufacturer. For the first measurement, only one test specimen was measured at 1 MPa. Then another test specimen was placed on top and measured with double the thickness. The last measurement included three test specimens with triple thickness. The following diagram was created from these three measured values.

Figure 12: Measurement values from the TIM test for the Spacecool test specimen. Three measurement values were determined for the stacked specimens. The results are shown with the linear regression line.

The thermal resistance in [K·cm²/W] is plotted on the y-axis. The x-axis represents the test specimen thickness in [cm]. The linear regression is plotted as a dotted line. The y-axis intercept represents the contact resistance of the test specimen, i.e. the coupling resistance to the measuring device. The reciprocal of the slope of the test specimen results in the lambda value [W/(cm·K)]. This slightly more complicated value is converted from [cm] to [m] to obtain the more common form [W/(m·K)]. The procedure for the measured values at 1.5 MPa is identical. In Table 1, the results of the TIM tester measurements on the Spacecool specimens are listed.

Table 1: Test results for the Spacecool specimens.

average specimen temperature / °C	nominal pressure / MPa	measured specimen thickness / mm	thermal conductivity / W·(m·K) ⁻¹	contact resistance / K·cm²·W ⁻¹
25	1	0.07	0.1605	1.55
25	1.5	0.07	0.1693	1.59

As the measuring device can only measure test specimen thicknesses of 0.1 mm or more according to its specifications, it can be assumed that the first measurement with a single test specimen will have a slightly larger measurement error. However, due to the very good regression, it is expected that the measurement was successful and that the measured values will all remain within the 5 % measurement uncertainty of the measuring device.

5.1.2 Measurements on the 3M Gen4 PRCF test specimen

To measure the 3M Gen4 PRCF test specimen, we had a sheet of the material with an adhesive layer on the backside, which was covered with a protective foil. To measure the material, the protective foil was removed, but the adhesive layer itself remained on the test specimen and is therefore included in the lambda value as part of the product. As before three 25 mm x 25 mm test specimens were cut from a large sheet of the specimen. For the first measurement, only one test specimen was measured at 1 MPa. Then another test specimen was placed on top and measured with double the thickness. The last measurement included three test specimens with triple thickness. The following diagram was created from these three measured values. In Figure 13, the test results of the TIM test on the 3M Gen4 PRCF test specimen is shown graphically. In Table 2, the test results are listed.

Figure 13: Measurement values from the TIM test for the 3M Gen4 PRCF test specimen. Three measurement values for the stacked test specimens are shown as well as the linear regression line.

Table 2: Test results for the 3M Gen4 PRCF specimens.

average specimen temperature / °C	nominal pressure / MPa	measured specimen thickness / mm	thermal conductivity / W·(m·K) ⁻¹	contact resistance / K·cm²·W ⁻¹
25	1	0.18	0.0931	8.99
25	1.5	0.18	0.0878	7.50

5.2 MDSC measurements

In Figure 14, the results of the MDSC measurements performed between -25 °C and 85 °C on the specimens “SPACECOOL” and “3M Gen4 PRCF” are shown. In Table 3, the specific heat capacity of these materials is listed at selected temperatures.

Figure 14: Results of the MDSC measurements on the specimens “SPACECOOL” and “3M Gen4 PRCF”.

Table 3: Experimentally determined specific heat capacity of the samples “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF” at selected temperatures.

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	specific heat capacity of “Spacecool” $c_p / \text{J}\cdot(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	specific heat capacity of “3M Gen4 PRCF” $c_p / \text{J}\cdot(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
-20	1.171 ± 0.059	0.931 ± 0.047
0	1.259 ± 0.063	0.995 ± 0.050
20	1.351 ± 0.068	1.055 ± 0.053
40	1.441 ± 0.072	1.115 ± 0.056
60	1.520 ± 0.076	1.186 ± 0.059
80	1.584 ± 0.079	1.268 ± 0.063

In Figure 15, the experimentally determined specific heat capacity of the three additional samples provided by SPACECOOL (sample 1, sample 2 and sample 3) are shown in the temperature range between $-25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $85\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Selected values of the specific heat capacity of these specimens are listed in Table 4. The relative expanded measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$) of these measurements according to GUM is $\pm 5\%$ [8].

Table 4: Experimentally determined values of the specific heat capacity of “sample 1”, “sample 2” and “sample 3” at selected temperatures.

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	specific heat capacity of sample 1 $c_p / \text{J}\cdot(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	specific heat capacity of sample 2 $c_p / \text{J}\cdot(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	specific heat capacity of sample 3 $c_p / \text{J}\cdot(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
-20	0.972 ± 0.049	0.919 ± 0.046	0.741 ± 0.037
0	1.048 ± 0.052	1.002 ± 0.050	0.795 ± 0.040
20	1.099 ± 0.055	1.078 ± 0.054	0.835 ± 0.042
40	1.153 ± 0.058	1.154 ± 0.058	0.880 ± 0.044
60	1.201 ± 0.060	1.191 ± 0.060	0.909 ± 0.045
80	1.240 ± 0.062	1.246 ± 0.062	0.945 ± 0.047

Figure 15: Results of the MDSC measurements performed on the three additional SPAECOOL samples “sample 1”, “sample 2” and “sample 3”.

5.3 LFA measurements

5.3.1 Measurements performed at CAE

LFA measurements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere at -20 °C, 0 °C, 20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C and 80 °C. At least five individual measurements were carried out on each sample to ensure that a stable measurement result was obtained. The average value from these five individual measurements is given as the resulting value. All measurements were performed with a pulse duration of 0.3 ms.

The measurements on the specimens “SPACECOOL” and “3M Gen4 PRFC: layer on substrate” were evaluated using the two-layer model, considering the thermophysical properties of the aluminium substrate which had been determined separately using MDSC and LFA measurements. The specimen “3M Gen4 PRFC” could also be examined experimentally as a free-standing single layer. The results of the LFA measurements on these two types of samples are listed in Table 5 and are shown in Figure 16. The relative expanded measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$) is ± 5 % according to GUM [8].

Table 5: Experimentally determined values of the thermal diffusivity of “Spacecool”, “3M Gen4 PRFC – 2-layer” and “3M Gen4 PRFC – freestanding”.

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	thermal diffusivity of “Spacecool” $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	thermal diffusivity of “3M Gen4 PRFC – 2- layer” $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	thermal diffusivity of “3M Gen4 PRFC – freestanding” $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
-20	0.097 ± 0.005	0.072 ± 0.004	0.064 ± 0.003
0	0.092 ± 0.005	0.070 ± 0.004	0.063 ± 0.003
20	0.083 ± 0.004	0.068 ± 0.003	0.061 ± 0.003
40	0.078 ± 0.004	0.066 ± 0.003	0.059 ± 0.003
60	0.072 ± 0.004	0.063 ± 0.003	0.057 ± 0.003
80	0.070 ± 0.004	0.061 ± 0.003	0.055 ± 0.003

Figure 16: Results of the LFA measurements on the specimens “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF”. The specimen “3M Gen4 PRCF” was examined as a free-standing layer as well as in a multilayer system consisting of aluminium and the PRCF film.

In Table 6, the experimentally determined values of the thermal diffusivity of “sample 1”, “sample 2” and “sample 3” are listed, whereas in Figure 17, the results of the flash measurements on the three additionally provided SPACECOOL samples are shown.

Table 6: Results of the flash measurements on the three additionally provided "Spacecool" samples "sample 1", "sample 2" and "sample 3".

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	thermal diffusivity of sample 1 $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	thermal diffusivity of sample 2 $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	thermal diffusivity of sample 3 $a / \text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
-20	0.120 ± 0.006	0.059 ± 0.003	0.183 ± 0.009
0	0.110 ± 0.006	0.051 ± 0.003	0.170 ± 0.009
20	0.100 ± 0.005	0.049 ± 0.002	0.153 ± 0.008
40	0.096 ± 0.005	0.047 ± 0.002	0.143 ± 0.007
60	0.089 ± 0.004	0.045 ± 0.002	0.135 ± 0.007
80	0.084 ± 0.004	0.043 ± 0.002	0.128 ± 0.006

Figure 17: Results of the LFA measurements on the specimens "sample 1", "sample 2" and "sample 3" by the manufacturer SPACECOOL.

5.3.2 Measurements performed at Netzsch

Flash measurements were also performed at the NETZSCH application laboratory on behalf of FIW. The laboratory received a SPACECOOL and a 3M Gen4 PRCF specimen on an aluminium substrate to determine the thermal conductivity of the coating. In the following, the results according to the report 9789-P-24 issued by NETZSCH Applikationslabor are detailed.

The measurements were performed using the NETZSCH LFA 467 HyperFlash® flash apparatus. The front side of the specimen is heated using a xenon flash lamp with adjustable energy by varying the voltage and pulse length. The resulting temperature increase on the rear side of the specimen is measured with an infrared detector (InSb or MCT). Software is used to control the test sequence and to collect and evaluate data. The high data acquisition rate of 2 MHz allows even very thin or highly conductive materials to be measured precisely. The built-in ZoomOptics optimises the detector's field of view, eliminating signal-distorting edge effects. Mathematical models enable correction calculations for finite pulse and heat loss effects. The LFA 467 complies with the national and international standards ASTM E-1461 and DIN EN 821. A detailed description of the laser flash process can be found in section 3.2.

Each specimen consists of an aluminium substrate with a polymer film bonded to it. The aim of the measurement was to determine the thermal conductivity of the polymer film. The LFA measurements were carried out in a standard specimen holder (\varnothing 12.7 mm) at 20 °C. Five individual measurements were carried out per specimen. The mean values of these individual measurements are shown in the results table. The front and back of the samples were coated with graphite in advance to increase their emissivity and absorptivity. The following table summarises the properties of the individual layers used to calculate the thermal conductivity of the specimens.

Table 7: Characteristics of the individual layers at 20°C.

characteristics	SPACECOOL	3M Gen4 PRCF
material of the substrate	aluminium	aluminium
thickness of substrate / mm	1.96 ± 0.01	1.96 ± 0.01
specific heat capacity of the substrate / J/(g·K)	0.885	0.885
density of the substrate / g/cm ³	2.70	2.70
thermal diffusivity of the substrate / mm ² /s	47.59	47.59
material of the coating	Polymer	Polymer
thickness of the coating / mm	0.11 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01
density of the coating / g/cm ³	1.351 ± 0.068	1.053 ± 0.053
density of the coating / g/cm ³	1.216 ± 0.061	0.84 ± 0.042

The adhesive layer between the aluminium substrate and the polymer film was not considered separately, but is included in the resulting thermal conductivity of the coating as contact resistance.

Table 8 summarises the measured and calculated temperature and thermal conductivity of the coating, including contact resistance (or adhesive layer) at 20 °C specimen

Table 8: Results of the flash measurements performed at Netzsch application laboratory.

test specimen	thermal diffusivity / mm^2s^{-1}	thermal conductivity / $\text{W}(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
SPACECOOL	0.106	0.174
3M Gen4 PRCF	0.043	0.038

Due to the specified tolerances in thickness ($\pm 10\%$ and 5% respectively), twice the error in thermal conductivity has to be expected. The thickness error is dominant in contrast to the errors in specific heat capacity and density. The errors in thermal conductivity (a), specific heat capacity (c_p) and density (ρ) of the coating are then incorporated into the thermal conductivity λ as a result of the error propagation law. The error in thermal conductivity can then be calculated using the following relationship

$$\lambda = a \cdot c_p \cdot \rho$$

With the 3M Gen4 PRCF specimen, additional uncertainty is to be expected due to a mismatch between the signal and the mathematical model, see Figure 18. An uncertainty of approximately $\pm 25\%$ is to be expected here.

Figure 18 Measurement signal (blue) and mathematical model (red) of the specimen 3M Gen4 PRCF.

5.4 Thermal conductivity calculated from MDSC and LFA measurements at CAE

Using the experimentally determined values density ρ , thermal diffusivity a and specific heat capacity c_p , the thermal conductivity λ of the specimens has been calculated. The results are listed in Table 9 and Table 10. Additionally the results are shown graphically in Figure 19 and Figure 20. The relative uncertainty of the thermal conductivity λ has been calculated according to the rules of uncertainty propagation, which leads to an relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for the thermal conductivity of $\pm 8.7\%$, which is below the target uncertainty of this deliverable.

Table 9: Calculated values of the thermal conductivity of the samples “Spacecool”, “3M Gen4 PRCF – 2-layer” and “3M Gen4 PRCF – freestanding”, determined by a combination of LFA and DSC measurements.

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	thermal conductivity of “Spacecool” $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	thermal conductivity of “3M Gen4 PRCF – 2-layer” $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	thermal conductivity of “3M Gen4 PRCF – freestanding” $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
-20	0.138 ± 0.012	0.056 ± 0.005	0.050 ± 0.004
0	0.141 ± 0.012	0.059 ± 0.005	0.053 ± 0.005
20	0.136 ± 0.012	0.060 ± 0.005	0.054 ± 0.005
40	0.137 ± 0.012	0.062 ± 0.005	0.055 ± 0.005
60	0.133 ± 0.012	0.063 ± 0.005	0.057 ± 0.005
80	0.135 ± 0.012	0.065 ± 0.006	0.059 ± 0.005

Table 10: Calculated values of the thermal conductivity of „sample 1”, “sample 2” and “sample 3”, determined by a combination of LFA and DSC measurements.

temperature $T / ^\circ\text{C}$	thermal conductivity of sample 1 $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	thermal conductivity of sample 2 $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$	thermal conductivity of sample 3 $\lambda / \text{W}\cdot(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
-20	0.159 ± 0.014	0.073 ± 0.006	0.340 ± 0.029
0	0.157 ± 0.014	0.068 ± 0.006	0.339 ± 0.029
20	0.149 ± 0.013	0.071 ± 0.006	0.320 ± 0.028
40	0.151 ± 0.013	0.073 ± 0.006	0.316 ± 0.027
60	0.145 ± 0.013	0.072 ± 0.006	0.308 ± 0.027
80	0.142 ± 0.012	0.072 ± 0.006	0.303 ± 0.026

Figure 19: Calculated thermal conductivity of the specimens “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF”.

Figure 20: Calculated thermal conductivity of the three additional samples provided by SPACECOOL.

5.5 Hot Disk method

The measurement results of the hot disk method, along with the input data used for calculations and a schematic illustration of the sample configurations, are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Samples and results of the Hot Disk measurements.

<p>1. 3M R&D PRCF Thermal conductivity: Aluminum (Al6060): 209 W/(m·K) Aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃): 40 W/(m·K) Glue: 0.14 W/(m·K)</p> <p>Results: PRCF film ($d = 200 \mu\text{m}$): 0.07 W/(m·K) Uncertainty: 0.02 W/(m·K) ($k = 2$)</p>	<p>The thickness of the aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃) was measured using a PHYNIX magnetic induction coating thickness gauge.</p>
<p>2. SPACECOOL Thermal conductivity: Aluminum (Al6060): 209 W/(m·K) Aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃): 40 W/(m·K) Glue: 0.14 W/(m·K)</p> <p>Results: SPACECOOL ($d = 100 \mu\text{m}$): 0.17 W/(m·K) Uncertainty: 0.04 W/(m·K) ($k = 2$)</p>	<p>Aluminum substrate with SPACECOOL film glued on. The thickness of the aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃) was measured using a PHYNIX magnetic induction coating thickness gauge.</p>
<p>3. "V98RF" Thermal conductivity: Aluminum (Al6060): 209 W/(m·K) Aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃): 40 W/(m·K)</p> <p>Results: PRC film ($d = 18 \mu\text{m}$): 0,03 W/(m·K) Uncertainty: 0.01 W/(m·K) ($k = 2$)</p>	<p>A selective emitting polymer "RF" on an aluminum plate, 0.8 mm thick. The thickness of the aluminum oxide film (Al₂O₃) was measured using a PHYNIX magnetic induction coating thickness gauge. Al₂O₃ = 10 μm; selective emitting polymer "RF" = 18 μm</p>
<p>4. SPACECOOL, Waterproof design</p> <p>Results: White side: 0.19 W/(m·K) Black side: 0.22 W/(m·K) Uncertainty White side: 0.04 W/(m·K) ($k = 2$) Uncertainty Black side: 0.05 W/(m·K) ($k = 2$)</p>	<p>Fully insulating material made of two layers of different colors.</p>

However, there are some recommendations for measurements of PRC samples to improve measurement accuracy:

- For thin samples of electrical insulating material, use a flexible sheet placed between two metal slabs or directly in contact with the conductive part of the sensor.
- Measurements require identical samples in duplicate, as single-sided testing is unsuitable for materials with low thermal conductivity (Hot Disk Analyzer Manual).
- Thin film samples on metal substrates should have thicknesses between 50 μm and 500 μm (Hot Disk Analyzer Manual).
- The probing depth should correspond to the sensor radius R , and the sample thickness should be at least 1.5–2 times R . The minimum available sensor radius is $R = 0.5$ mm. Multilayer structures can be used if necessary.
- To obtain accurate thermal conductivity values for thin PRC materials, remove the oxide film from aluminum substrates and avoid using adhesives to attach films to slabs.
- Surface roughness should be less than 1 μm , with up to 2 μm acceptable (Hot Disk Analyzer Manual).
- For PRC multilayer structures, a mathematical model is used to calculate the thermal conductivity of each thin film.
- Reference samples with varying thermal conductivity and thickness are required for each measurement mode to ensure accurate experimental results.

5.6 Compilation of the thermal conductivity

For some samples, the thermal conductivity was obtained with different experimental procedures, or sometimes even with the same procedure performed at different laboratories. A compilation of these data is shown graphically. In Figure 21, a comparison between the thermal conductivity values of “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF” obtained with the two different measurement methods is shown.

Figure 21: Comparison of the experimentally determined values of the thermal conductivity of “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF” that were obtained with a combination of LFA and MDSC measurements on the one hand and with the Hot Disk method on the other hand.

In Figure 22, a comparison of the thermal conductivity values of the additionally provided “Spacecool” samples determined with different measurement methods is shown.

Figure 22: Comparison of the thermal conductivity of the additional samples provided by Spacecool determined with different measurement methods.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable set out to identify and optimise transient methods for determining the thermal conductivity of thin PRC films and coatings with a target expanded uncertainty below 10 %. In line with Task 3.3 and Deliverable D6 of the PaRaMetriC work plan, two complementary routes (LFA and MDSC as well as TPS for comparison) have been implemented.

The resulting expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) meet the targeted objective:

- Thermal conductivity values derived from LFA and MDSC measurements achieved the typical relative expanded uncertainty of 8.7 % ($k = 2$) from -20 °C to 80 °C.
- TPS (hot disk) measurements for determining the thermal conductivity directly are mainly suitable for bulk materials and specific layered cases, but for thin coatings on metal substrates it exhibits higher relative expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) between 20 % and 30 %. Hence TPS has mainly been used for comparison.
- Thermal Interface Material (TIM) Tester from Linseis derived a typical relative expanded uncertainty of 5 % ($k = 2$).

The derived values for the thermal conductivities of the different samples are in a good agreement within the mentioned expanded uncertainties, especially for the samples “Spacecool” and “3M Gen4 PRCF”, but also for the Spacecool sample with waterproof design.

7. References

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